

The Influence of Organizational Culture and Job Competence on Employee Work Productivity at PT Patriot Intan Abadi, Tanah Laut Regency

Melania¹, Ketut Adi Saputra², Abdul Kadi³, Rifqi Amrulloh⁴

^{1,2,3,4} Pancasetia College of Economics Banjarmasin

ABSTRACT: This study aims to examine the influence of organizational culture and job competence on employee productivity at PT Patriot Intan Abadi, Tanah Laut Regency. The population in this study comprises all employees of PT Patriot Intan Abadi, totaling 137 employees. The sampling technique used in this research is probability sampling, employing the Taro Yamane or Slovin formula for calculation. Based on the Slovin formula calculation, the determined sample size is 58 respondents/employees. The data analysis used in this research is multiple linear regression with statistical tools facilitated by the IBM SPSS v.25 program. The results of this study indicate that organizational culture and job competence have an influence on the work productivity of employees at PT Patriot Intan Abadi. The job competence variable has a dominant influence on the work productivity of employees at PT Patriot Intan Abadi, Tanah Laut Regency.

KEYWORDS: Job Competence, Organizational Culture, Work Productivity.

INTRODUCTION

Human Resource Management (HRM) is a part of management science that aims to direct and manage human resources within a company to contribute according to the company's expectations. The success or failure of a company often depends on the ability to manage human resources, including in the era of the fourth industrial revolution (Industry 4.0). Human resources are a crucial factor in achieving the company's goals, and companies require competent and quality employees, especially in the era of globalization. HRM is a policy, practice, and system that influences the behavior, attitudes, and performance of company members. In this context, HRM is directed towards improving human capabilities to face competition and serves as a comparative strategy to influence company performance. Analyzing human resource needs is crucial for achieving the desired performance. HRM plays a role in developing and updating job existence, as well as creating activities and strategies to make a real contribution, enhance innovation, productivity, and work reputation within a corporate community.

One of the factors contributing to the improvement of HRM quality can be seen in work productivity. Enhancing labor productivity is a shared responsibility among various parties. Companies are responsible for providing tools, training facilities, and work infrastructure, while employees are expected to show high enthusiasm, discipline, and initiative to continually improve work results. Factors such as knowledge, skills, abilities, attitudes, and behaviors play a crucial role in achieving high work productivity. Productivity can be defined as the output of work within a unit of time required to produce products or services, involving human resources as a key factor. Work productivity is also related to both material and non-material aspects, including those that can or cannot be measured in monetary terms. Improving work productivity becomes a mindset that encourages employees to continually improve themselves, with the hope that today's conditions will be better than yesterday's. Overall, improving productivity is expected to ensure the efficiency and effectiveness of work, thereby supporting the achievement of company goals.

PT. Patriot Intan Abadi in South Kalimantan is one of the branches of a company headquartered in Jakarta that is engaged in layer chicken farming. PT. Patriot Intan Abadi consists of several farms (farm locations), including Liang Anggang HGU land (Sinar Farm), Bentok HGU land (Berlian Farm), Pulau Sari HGU land (Pulau Sari Breeding Farm), and Jaya Farm. The productivity of PT. Patriot Intan Abadi is assessed by how an employee achieves the targets set for themselves through the output generated by the employee. Below is the productivity table of PT. Patriot Intan Abadi for the year 2021.

Table 1. Productivity Data for Eggs from PT. Patriot Intan Abadi in 2021

Month	Egg Production Target (Units)	Actual Egg Production (Units)	Percentage
January	15.690.080	11.246.362	72%
Februari	16.664.580	11.156.480	67%
Maret	15.639.170	11.976.617	73%
April	15.850.580	11.744.276	74%
Mei	14.588.980	11.829.350	81%
Juni	14.563.510	11.093.935	76%
Juli	13.956.110	10.337.874	74%
Agustus	13.934.360	9.902.370	71%
September	12.911.860	9.994.883	77%
Oktober	12.890.860	9.343.335	72%
November	12.869.500	8.960.672	70%
Desember	12.875.500	10.075.434	78%
Rata-rata	14.369.590,83	10.595.132,33	73.85%

Source: Processed data

Based on Table 1, it can be observed that the target quantity at PT. Patriot Intan Abadi in the year 2021 did not consistently achieve the set target of 80%. The average, as seen, is only 73.85%. This indicates that the achievement of targets in 2021 was not optimal. The company's performance can be evaluated based on the overall achievement level of its work targets, which is significantly influenced by the individual performance of its employees. Thus, if employees can reach their individual targets, the company's overall work targets can be achieved. This demonstrates that the work productivity of each employee is not optimal, likely due to varying monthly performances and a decline in employee motivation to achieve work excellence

Factors influencing work productivity include organizational culture. Organizational culture is not just about whether employees like or dislike the culture; it is more about how they perceive the characteristics of that organizational culture. According to Sutrisno (2019:1), organizational culture refers to the norms prevailing in a company, as companies typically take the form of organizations involving cooperation among individuals forming groups or work units. In this context, organizational culture encompasses attitudes, values, rules, procedures, and guidelines that play a role in achieving the organization's vision and mission. The presence of organizational culture can help employees work effectively and avoid errors, including Human Error. PT Patriot Intan Abadi has its own organizational culture, manifested in the implementation of the 5S principles: Seiri (Sorting), Seiton (Setting in order), Seiso (Shining/Cleaning), Seiketsu (Standardizing), and Shitsuke (Sustaining). These principles provide guidelines and procedures for performing tasks.

In the observation results, the author identified several issues related to organizational culture at PT Patriot Intan Abadi, such as a lack of discipline among employees in adhering to “Seiso, Seiton, And Seiri” practices. There is a tendency for non-compliance with cleanliness practices, a lack of organization in arranging used equipment, and insufficient awareness in sorting equipment. Additionally, apart from organizational culture, another factor influencing work productivity is employee competence. Competency data indicates a low level of skills and knowledge across various divisions, with an overall competency percentage reaching only 37.96%. This low competency level is expected to impact a decrease in employee work productivity.

Based on the background described above, the problem formulations that can be derived are:

1. Does organizational culture and job competence significantly influence work productivity of employees at PT Patriot Intan Abadi, Tanah Laut Regency, individually?
2. Do organizational culture and job competence significantly influence work productivity of employees at PT Patriot Intan Abadi, Tanah Laut Regency, simultaneously?

3. Which one has a dominant influence on the work productivity of employees at PT Patriot Intan Abadi, Tanah Laut Regency?

LITERATURE REVIEW

a. *Human Resources Management*

Hasibuan in Nurbaya (2020) states that human resource management is the science and art of managing the relationships and roles of workers and jobs to be effective and efficient in helping achieve the company's goals and objectives. Simamora in Nurbaya (2020) defines human resource management as the utilization, development, assessment, reward provision, and management of individual members or groups. It also involves the design and implementation of planning systems, organization, development, career management, performance evaluation, compensation, and good labor relations. According to Nurbaya (2020), human resource management (HRM) has at least three main objectives:

1. Improve productivity levels.
2. Enhance the quality of work life.
3. Ensure that the company has fulfilled legal aspects.

The development of human resources (HR) is inseparable from the efforts made by every leader in the company. The development of both new and existing HR needs to be planned and continuous. Therefore, it is necessary to establish a human resource development program for employees. Employee development is increasingly deemed crucial due to the demands of jobs and positions as a result of advances in science and technology, as well as the intensification of competition among similar companies.

b. *Organizational Culture*

Understanding organizational culture cannot be separated from the basic concept of culture itself. Culture is a terminology widely used in the field of anthropology. Etymologically (origin of the word), organizational culture consists of two words: culture and organization. Soekanto in (Busro, 2018:1) explains that culture is the means of the community's works, feelings, and creations. Culture encompasses the entire understanding of social values, social norms, knowledge, as well as the overall social, religious, and other structures. According to Nawawi in (Busro, 2018:4), organizational culture or work culture is the repeated habits of employees in an organization. Morally, employees have agreed that these habits must be obeyed in the execution of work to achieve goals. Organizational culture essentially functions to regulate employees so that they understand how they should behave. According to Busro (2018), the functions of organizational culture are as follows:

1. Attitude towards their profession
2. Adaptation to colleagues and work environment
3. Reactive behavior towards leadership policies

Building organizational culture is not an easy task; it is challenging. It requires socialization and habituation efforts so that there is awareness to follow standard operating procedures (SOPs) and these SOPs become habits to follow the prevailing norms. Organizational culture grows because it is created and developed by individuals working in an organization, accepted as values to be upheld and passed down to every new member. These values serve as guidelines for every member while they are in the organizational environment and can be considered as distinctive features that differentiate one organization from another.

c. *Job Competence*

Job Competence is defined by Clark in Busro (2018) as follows: "competency is a knowledge or know-how for doing an effective job." Competence is knowledge or understanding of how to perform a job effectively. Meanwhile, according to Dessler (2017), competence is a personal characteristic that can be demonstrated, such as knowledge, skills, and personal behaviors like leadership. Competence is a perspective on human capabilities and knowledge, particularly the ability to meet various business needs by minimizing costs and optimizing customer service more, not less. Spencer & Spencer in Busro (2018) explain that competence differentiates job knowledge in the underlying behaviors of an employee within the organization. Job Competence can be divided into two categories:

1. Threshold competencies are essential characteristics (usually basic knowledge or skills like the ability to read) that someone must have to perform the job.
2. Differentiating competencies are factors that distinguish individuals with high and low competence

The concept of competence has begun to be applied in various aspects of human resource management, although it is most commonly used in training and development, recruitment, selection, and remuneration systems. Ruky in Busro (2018) states that the concept of competence has become increasingly popular and is widely used by large companies for various reasons, namely:

1. Clarifying work standards and expectations.
2. Employee selection tool.
3. Maximizing productivity.
4. Basis for developing remuneration systems.
5. Facilitating adaptation to change.

d. Work Productivity

According to Tohardi in E. Sutrisno (2017), work productivity is a mental attitude. It is a mindset that constantly seeks improvement over what already exists. It is a belief that one can perform better today than yesterday and tomorrow will be better than today. Meanwhile, according to Hasibuan in Busro (2018), productivity is the comparison between output (results) and input (input). If productivity increases, it will enhance efficiency (time-material-energy) and the working system, production techniques, and the improvement of skills of the workforce. There are many theories that discuss the factors influencing employee work productivity. Therefore, the researcher will cite several theories regarding the factors influencing employee work productivity. According to Simanjuntak in (Sutrisno, 2017:103), the factors influencing productivity include:

1. Training
2. Mental and physical capabilities of employees
3. Relationship between superiors and subordinates

According to Siagian (2002:55), efforts to improve productivity include:

1. Continuous improvement
2. Improvement in the quality of work results
3. Empowerment of human resources

Sutrisno (2016:104) states that to measure work productivity, the following indicators are needed:

1. Capability
2. Improvement in achieved results
3. Work enthusiasm
4. Self-development
5. Quality
6. Efficiency

e. Conceptual Framework

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

f. *Hypothesis*

The hypothesis proposed in this research is:

- H1 : The organizational culture and job competency, partially, have an impact on the work productivity of employees at PT Patriot Intan Abadi in Tanah Laut Regency.
- H2: Organizational culture and job competency, simultaneously, have an impact on the work productivity of employees at PT Patriot Intan Abadi in Tanah Laut Regency..
- H3: Job competency has a dominant influence on the work productivity of employees at PT Patriot Intan Abadi in Tanah Laut Regency.

RESEARCH METHOD

This research is a quantitative correlational study, which examines the relationship between independent and dependent variables. The population in this study consists of all employees of PT Patriot Intan Abadi, totaling 137 people. The sampling technique used in this research is probability sampling, employing the Taro Yamane or Slovin formula for calculation. Based on the Slovin formula calculation, the determined sample size is 58 respondents/employees. The data analysis used in this research is multiple linear regression with statistical tools facilitated by the IBM SPSS v.25 program.

RESULT

Validity Test

Table 2. The Result of Validity Test

Item	R Critical	Coefficient Correlation Value					
		Organizational Culture	Description	Job Competence	Description	Work Productivity	Description
1	0,30	0,554	Valid	0,419	Valid	0,406	Valid
2	0,30	0,341	Valid	0,503	Valid	0,699	Valid
3	0,30	0,391	Valid	0,500	Valid	0,574	Valid
4	0,30	0,527	Valid	0,594	Valid	0,738	Valid
5	0,30	0,600	Valid	0,453	Valid	0,525	Valid
6	0,30	0,415	Valid	0,479	Valid	0,553	Valid
7	0,30	0,487	Valid	0,523	Valid	0,346	Valid
8	0,30	0,683	Valid	0,613	Valid	0,383	Valid
9	0,30	0,546	Valid	0,577	Valid	0,544	Valid
10	0,30	0,587	Valid	0,564	Valid	0,467	Valid
11	0,30	0,696	Valid	0,548	Valid	0,525	Valid
12	0,30	0,444	Valid	0,495	Valid	0,624	Valid
13	0,30	0,489	Valid	0,546	Valid	0,314	Valid
14	0,30	0,514	Valid	0,434	Valid	0,631	Valid
15	0,30	0,469	Valid	0,591	Valid	0,772	Valid
16	0,30	0,426	Valid	0,427	Valid	0,699	Valid
17	0,30	0,535	Valid	0,755	Valid	0,673	Valid
18	0,30	0,442	Valid			0,552	Valid
19	0,30	0,523	Valid			0,482	Valid
20	0,30	0,592	Valid			0,486	Valid
21	0,30	0,491	Valid			0,448	Valid
22	0,30	0,473	Valid			0,441	Valid

Item	R Critical	Coefficient Correlation Value					
		Organizational Culture	Description	Job Competence	Description	Work Productivity	Description
23	0,30	0,510	Valid			0,612	Valid
24	0,30	0,415	Valid			0,684	Valid
25	0,30	0,516	Valid			0,683	Valid
26	0,30	0,427	Valid			0,218	Valid
27	0,30	0,462	Valid			0,792	Valid
28	0,30	0,407	Valid			0,623	Valid
29	0,30	0,319	Valid			0,400	Valid
30	0,30	0,328	Valid			0,652	Valid
31	0,30	0,641	Valid				
32	0,30	0,665	Valid				
33	0,30	0,561	Valid				
34	0,30	0,593	Valid				
35	0,30	0,378	Valid				

Source: Primary data processed

Data from Table 2 above, of the 35 statements on the organizational culture variable, all statement items are valid, for the work competency variable, all of the 17 statement items are proven to have valid values and then for the work productivity variable, all of the 30 statement items are declared valid because the coefficient is ≥ 0.30 .

Reliability Test

Table 3. The Result of Reliability Test

No	Variable	Cronbach's alpha	Sig	Description
1	Organizational Culture (X1)	0,906	> 0,7	Reliable
2	Job Competence (X2)	0,823	> 0,7	Reliable
3	Work Productivity (Y)	0,885	> 0,7	Reliable

Source: Primary data processed.

Based on Table 3 above, it is known that all variables are considered reliable. This is evidenced by the Cronbach's Alpha values being greater than the significance level (0.7).

Multiple Linear Regression

Regression analysis in this study aims to obtain hypothesis testing results regarding the influence of organizational culture and job competency on work productivity. The results of the multiple linear regression analysis in this study are as follows:

Table 4. Multiple Linear Regression Test

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	8.845	14.076		.628	.532
	Organizational Culture	.405	.110	.434	3.690	.001
	Job Competence	.779	.233	.393	3.342	.002

a. Dependent Variable: Produktivitas kerja

Source: Primary data processed.

Based on the above Table 4, the regression equation model is obtained as follows: $Y = 8,845 + 0,405X_1 + 0,779X_2 + \epsilon$

Based on the results of the equation above, it can be interpreted as follows:

1. The constant value (a) of positive 8.845 indicates that there is no increase in organizational culture and job competency variables; thus, work productivity is 8.845.
2. Organizational culture (X1) has a positive influence on work productivity, with a regression coefficient of 0.405. With this positive influence, it can be interpreted that there is a positive relationship between organizational culture and work productivity. The coefficient value of 0.405 implies that as the organizational culture variable increases, work productivity will increase, assuming all other independent variables remain constant.
3. Job competency (X2) has a positive influence on work productivity, with a regression coefficient of 0.779. With this positive influence, it can be interpreted that there is a positive relationship between job competency and work productivity. The coefficient value of 0.779 implies that as the job competency variable increases, work productivity will increase, assuming all other independent variables remain constant.

Analysis of Coefficient of Determination

The coefficient of determination is used to determine the role of all independent variables on the value of the dependent variable, as indicated by the magnitude of the coefficient of determination (R^2). The larger its value, the better the regression equation is at estimating the dependent variable.

Table 5. Coefficient of Determination

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.752 ^a	.565	.549	7.237
a. Predictors: (Constant), Kompetensi kerja, Budaya organisasi				

Source: Primary data processed

With a coefficient of determination of 0.565 or 56.50%, it can be interpreted that 56.50% of work productivity can be explained by the variables of organizational culture and job competency. Meanwhile, the remaining 43.50% is influenced by other variables not included in this research model.

Hypothesis Testing

Decision-making or hypothesis testing in this research involves using the t-test (partial) and the F-test (simultaneous). The results of the partial t-test and the simultaneous F-test in this study can be seen as follows:

1. t-Test

- a. Based on the results of hypothesis testing in Table 4, the significance level is $0.001 < 0.05$, so H_0 is rejected, and H_a is accepted. Therefore, it can be concluded that the hypothesis "there is a significant influence of organizational culture on work productivity" is proven.
- b. Based on the results of hypothesis testing in Table 4, the significance level is $0.002 < 0.05$, so H_0 is rejected, and H_a is accepted. Therefore, it can be concluded that the hypothesis "there is a significant influence of job competency on work productivity" is proven.

2. F-Test

The F-Square test is conducted to assess the goodness of the model. The F-Square values of 0.02, 0.15, and 0.35 can be interpreted to determine whether the latent variable predictors have a weak, medium, or strong influence on the structural level.

Table 6. The Result of F-Test

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	3740.039	2	1870.019	35.708	.000 ^b
	Residual	2880.375	55	52.370		
	Total	6620.414	57			
a. Dependent Variable: Produktivitas kerja						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Kompetensi kerja, Budaya organisasi						

Source: Primary data processed.

Based on Table 6 above, the Hypothesis Testing indicates a significance level of $0.000 < 0.05$, thus rejecting H_0 and accepting H_a . Based on the calculations above, it can be concluded that the hypothesis stating "there is a significant simultaneous influence of organizational culture and job competency on work productivity" is proven.

3. Dominant Variabel

To determine the independent variable that has the most dominant impact on variable Y, you can compare the regression coefficients (beta) between the variables. The independent variable with the most dominant impact on variable Y is the one with the largest regression coefficient. To compare the regression coefficients of each independent variable, you can refer to Table 4.11, where it is shown that variable X2 has the largest beta coefficient, which is 0.779. This means that variable Y is more dominantly influenced by variable X2 (job competency) compared to organizational culture variable (X1). The positive sign of the coefficient for variable X2 (job competency) implies that the better X2 (job competency) is applied or provided, the higher the work productivity of employees.

DISCUSSION

The Influence of Organizational Culture on Employee Productivity at PT Patriot Intan Abadi

Based on the analysis results, organizational culture has a positive and significant influence on employee productivity. For the organizational culture variable, the significance level is 0.001, thus it can be concluded that H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. This means that organizational culture influences employee productivity at PT Patriot Intan Abadi.

This implies that organizational culture affects the work productivity of employees at PT Patriot Intan Abadi. The culture developed by the organizational leadership is accepted as values that must be consistently implemented and maintained by all employees. These values are then considered as distinctive characteristics that differentiate a company from others. Organizational culture fosters identity in each employee and their commitment to the company because shared values make it easier for each employee to understand and appreciate every organizational event and activity. A strong culture implanted in a company will lead to the achievement of the company's vision, mission, and goals. A strategic culture can be used to achieve predetermined organizational goals. A strong culture can enhance work productivity. This is also supported by Colquitt and Wesson (2009:554), who state, "Although most companies strive to grow, not all companies have a culture that creates a sense of certainty about the norms and behaviors suitable for their employees. The strength of organizational culture emerges when employees definitively agree on the ways things should happen within the company. When their behavior is consistent with the envisioned expectations, a strong organizational culture has effectively united and directed employees."

This research is consistent with several previous studies, including the research conducted by Ainanur and Tirtayasa (2018), which found a positive and significant relationship between organizational culture and employee productivity. Another study by Zulfa (2021) also confirmed a positive and significant influence of organizational culture on employee productivity. Additionally, research by Marlina (2016) stated that organizational culture has a positive and significant impact on employee productivity.

The Influence of Job Competence on Employee Productivity at PT Patriot Intan Abadi.

Based on the results of the analysis conducted, job competency has a positive and significant influence on employee productivity.

For the job competency variable, the significance level is 0.002, thus it can be concluded that H₀ is rejected, and H_a is accepted. This means that job competency has an impact on employee productivity at PT Patriot Intan Abadi.

Outstanding competencies can enhance employee productivity. A company can achieve excellence when individuals working within the company can contribute maximally to the company according to their tasks and abilities. In other words, these individuals can work with optimal performance, achieving excellence in both current and future situations, in stable or changing conditions, without disrupting the work of others. Appropriate competencies are a determining factor for the excellence and performance of a company if the company has a strong foundation, reflected in all processes occurring within the company. According to Palan (2007:21), organizations are encouraged to focus on competencies, and organizations should always enhance employee competencies for them to perform and succeed. The high performance of employees will drive higher productivity.

This research is consistent with several previous studies, including the research conducted by Ainanur and Tirtayasa (2018), which found a positive and significant relationship between job competency and employee productivity. Other studies by Mulyadi (2010) and Sulfa (2021) also confirmed a positive and significant influence of job competency on employee productivity. Additionally, research by Marlina (2016) stated that competencies have a positive and significant impact on employee productivity.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the research and discussion, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. The organizational culture variable has a positive and significant influence on employee work productivity at PT Patriot Intan Abadi. This implies that an improvement in organizational culture will also enhance the work productivity of employees at PT Patriot Intan Abadi.
2. The Job Competence variable significantly influences the work productivity of employees at PT Patriot Intan Abadi. This means that the higher the job competency of employees, the higher their work productivity at PT Patriot Intan Abadi.
3. The Job Competence variable has a dominant influence on the work productivity of employees at PT Patriot Intan Abadi. This means that the job competency variable has the most significant contribution among the organizational culture variables to the work productivity of employees at PT Patriot Intan Abadi.

RECOMMENDATION

Based on the results of the discussion and conclusions, the recommendations from the results of this research are:

1. In the productivity variable, the employee skill indicators are inadequate, causing boredom when doing work, getting the lowest average score from other indicators and the sufficient score category, so the company management carries out training so that employee skills can improve. By increasing skills, employees can be creative and innovate at work so that boredom no longer occurs in doing their work.
2. Work Productivity Assessment for employees needs to be maintained and its benefits maximized, considering that there are many benefits that can be derived from this activity for companies to adopt strategic policies regarding the employment sector within their company.
3. It is better for the company to involve employees in every decision making and a leader must have a good relationship with employees so that employees have responsibility and contribute to advancing the company with all their abilities.
4. Companies should improve the quality of human resources, namely by holding training for employees at least once a year, so that each employee's self-development can continue to improve.

REFERENCES

1. Ainanur, Ainanur, and Satria Tirtayasa. 2018. "Pengaruh Budaya Organisasi, Kompetensi dan Motivasi Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan." *Maneggio: Jurnal Ilmiah Magister Manajemen* 1(1): 1–14.
2. Andi, and Eci Novita. 2016. "Pengaruh Kompetensi, Motivasi, Dan Kepuasan Kerja Terhadap Produktivitas Karyawan Pada PT. Perindustrian Dan Perdagangan Bangkinang." *Procuratio: Jurnal Ilmiah Manajemen* 4(2): 183–93.
3. BA Setiono, E Sustiyatik 2020 *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia (Pendekatan Teori dan Praktis)*, Surakarta: CV. Berkah Wisnu, 2020, <https://dspace.hangtuah.ac.id/xmlui/handle/dx/1006>

4. Beni Agus Setiono, Anton Respati Pamungkas, 2017 Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia Dan Perkembangan Global, CV. Berkah Wisnu, <https://dspace.hangtuah.ac.id/xmlui/handle/dx/1005>
5. Benny Agus Setiono, Ida Ayu Brahmastari, Siti Mujanah. 2017 Effect Of Safety Culture, Safety Leadership, And Safety Climate On Employee Commitments And Employee Performance PT. Pelindo III (Persero) East Java Province, Sebelas Maret Business Review, Vol. 3 Issue 1, pp. 6–10 <https://jurnal.uns.ac.id/SMBR/article/view/13680/22464>
6. Benny Agus Setiono. 2016 Pengaruh Budaya Organisasi, Karakteristik Individu, Karakteristik Pekerjaan Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan PT. Pelindo III Surabaya, Jurnal Aplikasi Pelayaran dan Kepelabuhanan Volume 6 Issue 2 Pages 128-146 <http://ojs.hangtuah.ac.id/ojs8/index.php/japk/article/view/30/25>
7. Busro, Muhamamad. 2018. Teori-teori Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia. Prenada Media.
8. Colquitt, Le Pine, and Wesson. 2009. Organizational Behaviour Improving Performance and Commitment Is the Work Place. Boston: McGraw-Hill Irwin.
9. Dessler, Gary. 2017. Human Resource Management. England: Pearson Education Limited, Inc.
10. Ghozali, Imam. 2018. Aplikasi Analisis Multivariate SPSS 25. 9th ed. Semarang: Universitas Diponegoro.
11. Marlina, Nina. 2016. “Pengaruh Budaya Organisasi, Kompetensi Dan Motivasi Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan PT. Taspen Kcu Bandung.”
12. Mulyadi, Hari. 2010. “Pengaruh Motivasi Dan Kompetensi Kerja Terhadap Produktivitas Kerja Karyawan Pada PT. Galamedia Bandung Perkasa.” Manajerial: Jurnal Manajemen dan Sistem Informasi 9(2): 97–111.
13. Nurbaya, Sitti. 2020. Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia Di Era Revolusi Industri 4.0. Makassar: Nas Media Pustaka.
14. Palan, R. 2007. Competence Management-A Practicionser’s Guide (Competency Management, Teknik Mengimplementasikan Manajemen SDM Berbasis Kompetensi Untuk Meningkatkan Daya Saing Organisasi) Penerjemah: Octa Melia Jalal. Jakarta: PPM.
15. Risnawan, Wawan. 2018. “Pengaruh Budaya Organisasi Terhadap Produktivitas Kerja Pegawai Di Dinas Cipta Karya, Kebersihan Dan Tata Ruang Kabupaten Ciamis.” Dinamika: Jurnal Ilmiah Ilmu Administrasi Negara 5(1): 83–92.
16. Robbins, Stephen P., and Tim Judge. 2013. Organizational Behavior. 15th ed. Boston: Pearson.
17. Siagian, Mauli. 2018. “Pengaruh Disiplin Kerja, Budaya Organisasi, Kompetensi, Dan Motivasi Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Pada Pt. Sat Nusapersada Tbk Batam.” Jurnal Akkrab Juara 3(1): 1–18.
18. Siagian, Sondang. 2002. Kiat Meningkatkan Produktivitas Kerja. Jakarta: Rineka Cipta.
19. Sugiyono, Sugiyono. 2016. Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif, Kualitatif, Dan R&D. Bandung: Alfabeta.
20. Sutrisno, Edy. 2016. Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia. Jakarta: Kencana.
21. Sutrisno, H Edy. 2019. Budaya Organisasi. Prenada Media.
22. Zulfa, Sela Indana. 2021. “Pengaruh Kompetensi dan Budaya Organisasi terhadap Produktivitas kerja Nelayan Grup Bintang Desa Pengembangan Kabupaten Jembrana.” undergraduate. Universitas Pendidikan Ganesha. <https://repo.undiksha.ac.id/5998/> (July 30, 2022).

Cite this Article: Melania, Ketut Adi Saputra, Abdul Kadi, Rifqi Amrulloh (2023). The Influence of Organizational Culture and Job Competence on Employee Work Productivity at PT Patriot Intan Abadi, Tanah Laut Regency. International Journal of Current Science Research and Review, 6(12), 7585-7594